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IMPACT OF CLIMATE ON GRAIN LEGUME YIELD STABILITY IN LONG-TERM EXPERIMENTS

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Diversifying rotations with grain legumes could contribute to the resilience of agricultural systems for adapting to climate change. Yield stability is an important goal in agricultural production and is particularly relevant in Europe-grown grain legumes. Their yields tend to be more variable than yields of some other crops and there is some evidence of a decrease in their yield stability over the last few decades. Currently, little is known about the relationship between yield stability of different grain legume species and changes in climate variability and extreme weather events. Analyses of such relationships and a fundamental understanding of the processes involved are needed to inform agronomy and plant breeding efforts to adapt grain legume cropping systems to climate change. We quantified changes in temporal yield stability using an adjusted coefficient of variation (aCV) and the influence of climate for pea and faba bean in three long-term experiments (LTE) in Borgeby (Sweden, 1960-2015), Berlin-Dahlem (Germany, 1953-2008) and Halle (Germany, 1950-2012). The objectives were to (i) quantify the relationship between climatic variability and yield stability for grain legumes under different bio-physical conditions, and (ii) quantify the effect of precipitation and temperature on yield stability. During the trial periods, temperature increased significantly in Borgeby, Berlin-Dahlem and Halle, by 1.7 °C, 1.6 °C and 1.3 °C, respectively. There was no trend in the annual precipitation across the sites. While yield instability of grain legumes increased significantly in Borgeby and Berlin-Dahlem this was not the case in Halle. In Borgeby and Berlin-Dahlem, there was a positive association between temperature (annual and April-July) and yield instability, and a positive relationship between temperature variability and yield instability. Annual precipitation did not affect yield stability but precipitation during specific periods did. In Halle, precipitation (April, June and July) was significantly and negatively correlated with yield stability of pea. We conclude that the analysis of LTEs enables detecting trends in yield stability changes over time. In the two sites with a higher increase in temperature (Borgeby and Berlin-Dahlem) there was a strong positive association between climate variability and yield instability for grain legumes which was not observed in Halle. This knowledge supports efforts in plant breeding and adapting the agronomic management of grain legumes to support the protein transition in Europe.

Keywords: *Climate change, faba bean, pea, pulses, yield variability*